

DEVELOPING GLOBAL SKILLS IN ELT CONTEXT: DIGITAL LITERACIES

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Abstract

This article is devoted to one of the cluster of the global skills. Furthermore, we are going to discuss about the notion of the digital literacies and give some recommendation about the effective ways of developing global skill cluster digital literacies.

Key words: global skills, digital literacy, communication, intercultural communication, critical thinking, English Language Teaching (ELT)

Ключевые слова: глобальные навыки, цифровая грамотность, коммуникация, межкультурная коммуникация, критическое мышление, преподавание английского языка (ПАЯ)

Таянч сўзлар: глобал кўникмалар, рақамли савотхонлик, алоқа, маданиятлараро алоқа, танқидий фикрлаш, инглиз тилин ўқитиш (ИТЎ)

Teachers face with challenging task as in the rapidly changing world to equip their learners with life-long skills which will give to learners chance to survive in this modern jungle. Still the English language keeps the leading position as the language of international culture and commerce, so that learners of ours as current and future global citizens, students must learn how to deal with global issues in English using a blend of social, cognitive and emotional skills and competencies.[1:87]

Global skills can be grouped into five clusters, all of which are relevant to the ELT context (See 1-scheme):

Scheme-1

Global skills clusters

The given scheme visually shows that global skills are integrative way of dealing the life teaching and the reason of choosing “digital literacies” also related with one of the modern problems of society and education. Technology has become an integral part of modern life. During language classes, we can give students opportunities to use technology to solve problems and be creative.[3:76]

Recommendations:

Here are some activities which prepare a digitally literate ELT student.

- Use social media for learning and collaborating. For example, Facebook or LinkedIn groups can be used to connect and collaborate with their peers. Teachers can create group chats for the students to share information, audio resources, videos, etc.
- Guide on how to avoid plagiarism. For example, students often copy ideas and use phrases they find online without providing proper reference to the original sites.
- Provide authentic contexts for practice. For example, when teaching students about the importance of managing their online identity, they can be assigned to research themselves online to find out what a potential employer would see. This can be followed up with a discussion about their findings, and have them list some of the things they were proud of as well as some of the things they’d like to change. This can be a great lesson idea for Business English lessons. [5:465]
- If you want students to become sophisticated users of technology, it’s important to guide them out of their comfort zone. For example, some students may be

quite good at communicating in short and distinct paragraphs and hashtags on Twitter or Instagram, so moving out of their comfort zone will mean sharing their opinion through a lengthier blog post. If they are good at blogging, they can experience video journals or podcasts.

To put it simply, global talents are those that are necessary for success in the uncertain and fast changing 21st-century environment as well as for being a lifelong learner. Teachers need to prepare their kids for scenarios and careers that don't yet exist and that we can't anticipate with certainty [6:54]

Global skills may be used to all courses and to life after school; they are not limited to any one subject on the curriculum.

The device also gathers data on any detrimental effects on infant development. In terms of psychology, childhood is a time where kids learn to know things they don't yet know. The children's development will be hindered if they are already addicted to the device and it has a detrimental impact on their youth.

Global skills can be grouped into five clusters, all of which are relevant to the ELT context.

- communication and collaboration
- creativity and critical thinking
- intercultural competence and citizenship
- emotional self-regulation and wellbeing
- digital literacies.

While most teachers would agree that it is their duty to promote global literacy in their classrooms, it can be difficult to understand how this can be accomplished when there is already a time crunch. If we are to meet this challenge, we must find methods to include global skills in the curriculum without adding to our own burden or taking away from valuable class time [7:56].

Think-pair-share

In a conventional classroom, the teacher will assign pupils to do a task on their own and then verify (discuss) the results with the class. The same steps are taken in the think-pair-share approach, but before the final checking stage, the instructor instructs the class to compare responses in pairs (pair). Even though this stage only lasts for around 15 to 30 seconds in total, the advantages are substantial since it fosters critical thinking, communication, and teamwork as well as student motivation and enhanced self-assurance.

Evaluating in terms of one's own culture

There is cultural material or distinct cultural sections in many ELT course books. By encouraging them to discuss the parallels and contrasts between what is written in the course book and their personal context, the instructor may get students involved in this. Even if the pupils' level of language is limited, this is doable. For instance, if the topic of the lesson is what a person from a specific nation consumes for breakfast, the instructor may put the foods on the board and then ask the students to identify which ones are comparable to or dissimilar to what they would have for breakfast. The teacher might provide the students the English names for the regional foods. Students might then proceed by utilizing both lists to create their ideal breakfast [8:76].

The choice between writing and filming videos

Teachers might provide students the option of submitting their work as a video clip when assigning assignments that are traditionally written, such as book reports, summaries, project final products, etc. This encourages them to work on the majority of the five clusters listed above. It also has the added benefit of enabling dyslexic students to excel without having to worry about others criticizing their spelling and handwriting or having to purposefully use simple vocabulary because it would take too long to find the correct spelling of the words they would like to use. Many students really put more effort into creating a video than a written piece of paper, especially if they know this will be shared and evaluated by fellow students [9:89].

CONCLUSION

Global Skills are the knowledge, talents, and skills that all degree and certificate candidates are anticipated to possess upon graduation. Faculty at LCC created this list of learning objectives to serve as the cornerstone for all of the college's courses, programs, certifications, and degrees. Since the world is changing so quickly, it is difficult for educators to even begin to predict the kinds of skills and competencies that their students will require in 10, 20, 30, or even 50 years. But it is obvious that standard academic courses on their own won't be sufficient. Life skills education is already a common component of many curricula throughout the world. Many instructors are now required to incorporate the teaching of these abilities into their subject-matter instruction, which has become the standard. However, the assistance and preparation given to teachers differs greatly. Our Position Paper is intended to support ELT instructors in particular in helping to reflect on and create sustainable approaches to teach global skills alongside their language learning objectives.

Vital thinking abilities are more vital than ever in the age of "fake news"! Asking older students to analyze several news pieces as part of a lengthier project might assist them in developing these abilities.

Pick a recent news story to discuss with your students. Give them a news story or newspaper article on the subject, then instruct them to discuss it with a partner. Next, study the same story in several media outlets with the students. Ask them to take into account the author, the target audience, the emotions present, and the techniques employed to pique the reader's interest.

Do you wish to foster digital literacy in your students at the same time? Request that your pupils verify one of the articles online, using more than one source of information. They should think about which source is the most reliable and which to trust.

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